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Alternative Paths in Conflict Resolution and Their Advantages in Meeting Social Demands

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Abstract—This research addresses the importance of alternative paths in conflict resolution and their advantages in meeting social demands, aiming to contribute to faster and more inclusive justice. The judicial system faces a growing number of disputes, and in response to this overload, Alternative Dispute Resolution Methods (ADRs) such as mediation, conciliation, arbitration, and Online Dispute Resolution (ODR) have gained prominence. These methods offer collaborative and more economically accessible solutions, helping to reduce pressure on the system and facilitate access to justice. The study also considers other practical approaches, such as the ombudsman and Malpractice Screening Panels, which are effective in resolving specific disputes and building consensus on technical matters. Additionally, the article explores the origins of multi-door systems—a structured approach to selecting the most appropriate resolution method based on the nature of each case. The methodology is based on a bibliographic review, including scientific articles and specialized studies on ADRs. The research also examines challenges such as communication breakdowns and differing legal perceptions between parties, concluding that ADRs are essential for a more efficient judicial system that responds more effectively to contemporary social needs.

Index Terms—Alternative Conflict Resolution Methods, Mediation, Conciliation, Arbitration, Conflict, Access to Justice, Multiport.

I. INTRODUCTION

This research aims to analyze the importance of Alternative Paths in Conflict Resolution and their Advantages in Meeting Social Demands, with a focus on the main Alternative Dispute Resolution Methods (ADRs). Efficient conflict management has become a pressing need in the current legal landscape, where the judicial system faces an increasing overload of cases that compromise both the speed and accessibility of justice. In response, multi-door systems have emerged, allowing for the selection of different resolution methods according to the nature of the dispute and the profile of the parties involved.

Throughout this study, the main ADRs used in Brazil will be explored—namely mediation, conciliation, arbitration, and Online Dispute Resolution (ODR), among others—evaluating the characteristics and applications of each. These methods aim not only to relieve the judiciary but also to offer more collaborative and agile alternatives, promoting a more inclusive and accessible approach to justice that meets diverse social needs. The relevance of this analysis lies in the ability of ADRs to address a wide range of conflicts more efficiently, respecting party autonomy and prioritizing consensual solutions. The methodology is based on bibliographic research, supported by scientific articles, books, and specialized studies that highlight both the advantages and challenges of these methods, with the objective of understanding to what extent they contribute to a more effective justice system adapted to contemporary needs.

II. CONFLICT MANAGEMENT

From birth to death, humans interact in pursuit of development in all areas of life. The desire to build, to engage in buying and selling, and to seek new spaces is inherent to human coexistence. In groups, humans are able to use nature's many resources more efficiently.

Author Sidney Guerra teaches the following:

A person, upon birth, feels the need to find their place in society, and the socialization process lasts a lifetime. This process is characterized by 'teaching' the individual how to participate in society, which represents a major learning process.

This occurs because a person must be trained to fulfill the various roles that society presents.

Aristotle stated that every city is a form of association, and that every association is formed for a reason—that is, for some kind of benefit. If, even in his time, the renowned Greek philosopher mentioned the pursuit of profit, it is evident that in today's globalized world, where capital is dominant, the need to adapt to this new paradigm is of utmost importance.

With globalization weakening borders more and more, human interactions have become increasingly intense. A wide range of people interact daily, both in person and online, which increases the chances of disagreements.

The word *conflict* comes from the Latin *conflictus*, and carries the idea of clash, struggle, or fight. According to Douglas H., conflict can be defined as:

“Conflict can be defined as a process or state in which two or more people diverge due to individual goals, interests, or objectives, perceived as mutually incompatible.”

According to Dora Schnitman:

Conflicts are inherent to human life, as people are different, have personal and unique views of reality, and, as a result, express differing—often clashing—perspectives. The way conflicts are addressed becomes a key point when aiming to establish harmony in daily relationships. One could say that conflicts occur when at least two independent parties perceive their goals as incompatible and, therefore, identify the need for third-party involvement to achieve their aims.

Conflicts generally cause dissatisfaction between the parties and can arise for several reasons, such as: conflicting interests, power disputes, incompatible goals, competition for limited resources, and differing viewpoints.

The most important concept is **dialogue**. As a tool for conflict resolution, dialogue is essential for preserving social

relationships. It invites participants to step away from their own interests and needs to work toward solutions that benefit everyone involved. Only through communication can people be encouraged to value differences and broaden the range of possible solutions that serve all parties.

In Brazil, the so-called “Gerson’s Law” still prevails—where people often try to gain an advantage in every situation. This reflects a general inability to make concessions. As individuals often lack the social and emotional skills to resolve their issues autonomously, they turn to the State excessively, even for minor disputes that could be settled without resorting to the judicial system. Moreover, there is still an idealized notion of the State as the sovereign force that ensures protection and order for all, as described by English philosopher Thomas Hobbes in his classic work *Leviathan*.

On the other hand, many people see conflict as something that only brings discomfort, strain, or wasted time, and therefore try to avoid it at all costs. However, it’s important to emphasize that conflict can lead to debate and, consequently, new ideas. Thus, disagreement is not inherently negative—the way we handle it is what can lead to different outcomes.

III. ORIGINS OF MULTI-DOOR SYSTEMS

The mechanism known as the Multi-Door System emerged from a conference held in 1976, which addressed the inability of the U.S. judiciary to handle the growing number of legal demands. At that event, Harvard Law School professor Frank Ernest Arnold Sander introduced the concept of the *Multi-Door Courthouse System*, a model that has since evolved to meet the growing complexity of modern disputes.

According to this theory, the implementation of a multi-door conflict resolution system is based on four essential pillars:

- 1) The institutionalization of alternative dispute resolution methods;
- 2) The selection of the appropriate method through screening conducted by an expert;
- 3) Adequate training of professionals who will manage conflicts through these methods, including lawyers and mediators/conciliators;
- 4) The establishment of public policies to raise awareness about the benefits of alternative methods, as well as the proper allocation of resources and the resulting cost savings for the judicial system through the encouragement of Alternative Dispute Resolution (ADR) methods.

Professor Sander envisioned a broad multi-door system with a wide range of “doors” for conflict resolution, in which each case would be assessed and directed to a procedure best suited to resolving that specific issue. He emphasized:

In the future, there will not be simply a courthouse, but rather a specific dispute resolution center or a multi-door courthouse in which litigants would be screened and channeled to a variety of dispute resolution mechanisms, such as mediation, arbitration, superior court, fact-finding, ombudsman, or malpractice screening panels.

Fact-finding refers to a process where the parties delegate to a third party the task of investigating and clarifying the facts

related to the conflict. It is commonly applied in international law. As explained in legal doctrine:

Fact-finding is essentially a mechanism for investigating conflicting facts, serving as a preparatory act for other peaceful means of dispute resolution. It may include the proposal of recommended behaviors for the parties, which makes it an investigative and preliminary tool, conducted by one or more investigators or a commission, either under the rules of an international organization (political means) or through a separate agreement (diplomatic means).

One example of fact-finding is the International Commission of Inquiry on Syria, established to investigate human rights violations during the Syrian civil war.

The term ombudsman, of Swedish origin, means “listener” or “representative.” In Scandinavian countries, the ombudsman is a public official tasked with addressing citizens’ complaints and concerns. It functions similarly to a mediator. Ombudsman offices offer a suitable space for resolving conflicts between citizens and institutions and can serve as a strategic management tool. The role can exist in journalism, businesses, and public organizations.

The malpractice screening panel operates as a filter to assess the presence of negligence, recklessness, or lack of skill. Parties submit the matter to an impartial technical expert, who evaluates whether any of these elements contributed to the conflict. This tool is especially useful in disputes involving medical errors, traffic accidents, or incidents involving firearms. It is particularly effective in cases that rely heavily on technical or factual analysis requiring expert input.

On pre-trial methods, Judge Vivian Carla Josefovicz notes:

In the United States, there is a wide variety of conflict resolution methods (mini-trial, neutral evaluation by a third party, summary jury trial, private judging, etc.), always aiming to choose the most appropriate solution for each conflict, and allowing even the combination of such methods. This is known as the *multi-door courthouse* system, which seeks to provide the best possible means for resolving a particular dispute.

ADR gained visibility and broader acceptance with the enactment of the Alternative Dispute Resolution Act (ADRA) in 1998. Regarding ADR, it is important to note:

Some ADR procedures are mandatory, while others—the majority—are voluntary. However, even when certain ADR steps are required, their outcome is never binding, since the interested party can always request a new judgment from the regular courts. Essentially, it serves as a simple procedural condition for filing a civil action.

In Brazil, alternative dispute resolution methods are mainly focused on conciliation, mediation, and arbitration, whereas in the United States, the ADR system includes a much broader range of mechanisms.

The Multi-Door Justice System was introduced in Brazil in 2010 through Resolution 125 of the National Council of Justice (CNJ), which established the National Judicial Policy for the

proper treatment of conflicts of interest within the Judiciary. The goal is to foster a new culture of self-composition, empowering the parties themselves to reach a fair solution. This represents a modern interpretation of the principle of access to justice, granting greater autonomy to litigants and moving beyond the traditional view that only judges should be responsible for resolving disputes.

IV. MAIN ALTERNATIVE DISPUTE RESOLUTION METHODS (ADRS) IN BRAZIL

Access to justice in Brazil began to be actively encouraged, especially with the 1988 Federal Constitution, particularly in consumer-related matters, as buying and selling products and services form the foundation of capitalism. From a strictly legal perspective, it can be said that conciliation methods are not sufficiently promoted or encouraged by the judiciary. For example, in the state of Pernambuco, “for every 100 cases scheduled for a hearing, only three result in an agreement. Most companies show extremely low conciliation rates,” according to information published on the website of the National Council of Justice (CNJ).

Initially, CNJ Resolution No. 125/2010 set out the first guidelines on ADR methods in Brazil. Later, the 2015 Civil Procedure Code, in Article 3, consolidated these guidelines by stating that conciliation, mediation, and other methods of consensual conflict resolution should be encouraged by judges, lawyers, public defenders, and members of the Public Prosecutor’s Office—even during the course of a judicial proceeding.

A. Mediation

Mediation is a conflict resolution method in which a third party, neutral and impartial, facilitates dialogue between the parties so that they themselves can, with autonomy and balance, develop the best solution to the dispute. It is a structured procedure, which may or may not end in an agreement, since the parties have autonomy to seek solutions that reconcile their interests.

What are the applicable principles? Impartiality of the mediator, equality between the parties, orality, informality, party autonomy, search for consensus, confidentiality, and good faith—all of which are provided for in Law No. 13,140/2015. Mediation is often used in family and neighborhood disputes.

B. Conciliation

In conciliation, the third-party facilitator plays a more active role and may suggest solutions, while remaining neutral toward the conflict and impartial between the parties. It is a quick consensual process aimed at achieving social harmony through a balanced solution. The same principles that apply to mediation are also applicable to conciliation, according to Law No. 13,140/2015.

At first glance, both methods seem very similar. However, the Civil Procedure Code, in Article 165, makes a distinction: the conciliator usually acts in cases where there is no pre-existing relationship between the parties, while the mediator works in disputes involving ongoing or past relationships.

It is worth noting that many courts in Brazil now have Judicial Centers for Conflict Resolution and Citizenship (CE-JUSCs), which are structured to enable parties to resolve their disputes through self-composition.

C. Arbitration

The word *arbitration* originates from the Latin term *arbiter*, meaning “judge” or “juror.” It is likely that arbitration predates all formal legal systems. It is a method of heterocomposition, where a decision is rendered by a third party. Arbitration has its roots in the need to resolve conflicts arising from commercial relationships.

In this method, the parties authorize arbitrators—typically professionals with deep knowledge in the matter—to decide the issue. In Brazil, arbitration is regulated by Law No. 9,307/96. The 2017 labor reform allowed arbitration to resolve individual labor disputes under the conditions established in Article 507-A of the CLT (Labor Code). Even the Federal Constitution, in Article 114, §1, allows arbitration in collective labor disputes.

Judge Fernando Montefusco stated:

If Brazilian society used arbitration more often to resolve its conflicts, not only would it speed up procedures, but it would also help reduce the number of court cases, and we could potentially increase Brazil’s GDP by 25%.

D. Online Dispute Resolution (ODR)

Online Dispute Resolution (ODR) refers to resolving conflicts via the internet and is also considered an important ADR method. These are digital platforms where litigants can negotiate online. There are several such platforms, including SquareTrade, one of the pioneers in ODR, used by eBay, and Consumidor.gov, a Brazilian government initiative.

In addition, Brazil’s new Public Procurement Law (Law No. 14,133/21) provides, in Article 151, for the use of dispute resolution committees, which can also be considered a form of ADR. However, this tool is still used modestly in practice.

V. ADVANTAGES AND CHALLENGES OF ALTERNATIVE DISPUTE RESOLUTION METHODS

The institutionalization of Alternative Dispute Resolution (ADR) methods brings significant benefits to the judicial system, especially by reducing the use of public resources. When parties choose self-composition or arbitration, they avoid the need for judicial intervention, allowing resources such as court staff, judges, physical infrastructure, and technology to be redirected to other cases. This contributes to a more efficient and faster judicial system, relieving case backlog and making justice more accessible to all.

Additionally, ADR methods can facilitate access to justice for underprivileged groups, as they often eliminate travel expenses, with conflict resolution occurring through digital platforms in some cases—providing greater convenience to all involved. Another key advantage is that the solutions are consensual and, therefore, tend to be longer-lasting, as the parties actively participate in the negotiation process, make mutual concessions,

and promote more effective and satisfactory outcomes for both sides.

However, it is also important to acknowledge the existing challenges. Several variables must be considered, as noted by professors Gabbay, Falleck, and Tartuce:

- (i) Communication failures, (ii) the need to express emotions, (iii) different interpretations of facts, (iv) different views on the law, (v) personal principles, (vi) pressure from the client, (vii) links to other disputes, (viii) the presence of multiple parties, (ix) agency conflicts, and (x) the ‘jackpot syndrome’—the tendency to take risks in hopes of a maximum reward—and excessively litigious attorneys.

Therefore, for the use of ADR methods to become more firmly established, it is essential that parties are prepared to face these challenges with the support of skilled negotiators and a shared commitment to peaceful and fair conflict resolution.

VI. FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

ADR methods aim at promoting social peace, as they seek to resolve conflicts in a less bureaucratic way than traditional judicial proceedings. Access to justice is a constitutional right; however, depending on the type of dispute, formal litigation is not always necessary. Through mediation, conciliation, arbitration, or other dispute resolution methods, parties can settle conflicts either autonomously (as in mediation or conciliation) or through third-party decisions (as in arbitration). Social peace should not be the exclusive responsibility of the State, since individuals themselves can independently negotiate and resolve their disputes, thus fostering peace and social well-being.

It is necessary to invest in greater public awareness of self-composition so that all parties involved fully understand the terms of any agreement and recognize the importance of making concessions in order to reach a reasonable solution. The path will be long, especially considering the Brazilian cultural tendency to “always seek personal advantage,” which often results in a lack of willingness to compromise.

The role of democracy is not to eliminate conflict, but to create peaceful ways of resolving it, with the goal of producing positive change in social relationships and in the way the State functions.

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